

A MICROMECHANICAL AND CHEMICAL STUDY OF THE INTERFACIAL BOND
IN CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A study of the complex nature of the interface in carbon-fibre epoxy resin composites is presented in which a range of experimental techniques have been applied. This includes an XPS analysis of the fibres, which reveals the chemistry and microporous structure of the surface. Additionally a spatial chemical characterisation of composite fracture surfaces at a resolution of 0.2 μm , was conducted, using scanning SIMS.

Increasing the degree of fibre oxidative treatment affects an improvement in the adhesive interfacial bond. The use of scanning SIMS provides clear and unambiguous evidence of the presence or absence of relatively thin matrix overlayers remaining on fibres within a fracture surface, in contrast to conventional electron microscopy.

INTRODUCTION

The use of surface oxidation to promote the adhesion of carbon fibres to epoxy resins has been known for some time. However, in attempts to understand the mechanism of the process, a number of conflicting results have been reported and therefore the true nature of the adhesive bond is still a subject of some controversy. We have therefore embarked upon a programme intended to correlate interfacial bond strength with the surface chemistry of the fibres. In the first stage of the work [1,2] the use of a barium labelling technique for x-ray photoelectron spectroscopic analysis (XPS)

was developed. The labels enable the relatively small surface concentrations of acid groups to be quantitatively analysed. Analysis of a series of fibre samples with increasing degrees of fibre treatment (oxidation), denoted DFT, showed that the concentrations of carboxylic acid groups and chemisorptive sites, in which the latter appear to adsorb water molecules, increased accordingly. Since these are strong contenders for forming a chemical type of interfacial bond with resin molecules, it was essential to develop techniques which enable the rôle of both species to be elucidated.

Additionally the adsorption, or penetration, of resin molecules into fibre surface micropores which probably have widths ≤ 1 nm is a potentially important factor in this context. Following on from the previous success of our labelling approach, in the present work the technique has been extended to micropores in which these are filled with a suitable molecule for detection by XPS. Several molecules were considered, and chloroform emerged as the most appropriate candidate since it has a dimension ~ 0.5 nm, does not react chemically with functional groups or surface carbon atoms under labelling conditions, and can be differentiated from the other species normally present on a fibre through detection of the halogen atom.

Preliminary trial experiments confirmed the suitability of this labelling reagent, especially as the specific micropore volumes derived from the spectral data were within the expected range [3]. We have therefore used this technique to explore the fibre surface structure at the molecular level.

An assessment of the actual mechanical strength of the interfacial bond is also required. There are several approaches to this, one of which is to study the nature of the fracture surface of a composite specimen, created in a simple bend or shear test. Dependent upon the relative strength of the interface and matrix, conventional scanning electron microscopy could be used to search for the presence or absence of resin overlayers or remnants which adhere to the fibres. However, in the event of relatively thin overlayers being present, possibly of the order of ~ 10 nm in thickness, these would be at the limit of detectability. We have therefore applied an alternative approach, which provides a chemical "map" with $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ lateral resolution of the fracture surface where there are $\sim 7 \mu\text{m}$ diameter fibres, having an analysis depth of only a few nanometers. Secondary ion mass spectrometry is a well-known technique where an energetic primary beam (e.g. Ga^+ at 10 kV, 0.1 nA) is used to sputter the surface, and the

resulting secondary ion emission analysed by a mass spectrometer. Focussing and rastering the primary beam gives a corresponding spatial resolution of surface chemistry, and in our case, the mass spectrometer is "tuned" to secondary ions characteristic of the two components present; fibre and matrix. This novel approach has proved to be particularly appropriate in this project.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

1. Fibres

Lengths of "tow" (6,000 x 7 μm filaments) were provided by Drs Dorey and Harvey, Royal Aircraft Establishment, Farnborough, which had been surface treated (oxidised) with a range of degrees of fibre treatment (DFT) quantified on a scale from 0 to 100% DFT; 100% approximating to a commercial level. Several meters of tow were available, at each DFT, some of which was analysed by labelling and XPS, and the remainder used for the fabrication of composite specimens.

2. X-ray Photo Electron Spectroscopy of Chloroform Labelled Type I Carbon Fibres

A \sim 10 cm length of tow was immersed in 75 ml of fresh AR grade chloroform whilst gently boiling (under reflux, 61°C) for 1 hour. Transference to a circulating air oven at 80°C for a further hour ensured a removal of excess reagent. The sample was mounted for XPS across a gap in a metal holder, for analysis on a VG Scientific ESCA 3MKII, interfaced to a PDP8e data system at the Department of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Surrey. The specimens were analysed by a combination of wide survey scans covering 0 to 1000 eV photoelectron binding energy and narrow scans, 20 eV in width, centered on the respective peak positions of the relevant elements, (C, O, N and Cl). Integration after background subtraction of peak areas enabled the elemental surface atomic percentages to be derived, using published sensitivity factors [1,2].

3. Fractured Uni-directional Composites for SIMS Analysis

Standard interlaminar shear test samples were fabricated by Dr J. Harvey of the R.A.E., using XA fibres at three levels of surface treatment:- untreated (0% DFT or UT), intermediate ($\bar{\sim}$ 40% DFT or IT) and high ($\bar{\sim}$ 75% DFT or HT). An anhydride cured epoxy resin (Shell Epikote 828/Epikure NMA/K61b) was used to fabricate specimens for testing according to the accepted standard [4]. The corresponding transverse fracture surfaces were analysed with scanning SIMS.

Specimens were mounted on metal stubs and analysed with a VG SIMSLAB

instrument fitted with a MIG100 Ga metal ion gun and MM12-12 quadropole mass spectrometer. A compensating electron flood of 500 eV, 5nA cm⁻², from a VGLEG 31 gun, was used to maintain a steady surface potential during image acquisition. These experiments were conducted in the Surface Analysis Service Laboratory, Chemistry Department, of the University of Manchester Institute of Science and Technology. The spectrometer is interfaced to a VG5100 Framestore system, permitting acquisition, storage and processing of images and spectra. In scanning mode a lateral resolution of 0.2 μm can be attained and up to four secondary ions can be detected in a given acquisition sequence. Multiple overlaying of selected images enables accurate positional comparisons to be made between features with contrasting surface chemistries.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Surface Chemistry and Structure from XPS Analysis

A typical XPS spectrum is given in Fig.1, showing the positions of the peaks of interest, together with derived surface atomic percentages. Note that although the Cl peak at 200 eV is only just detectable on the wide spectrum a narrow scan centered at this binding energy shows a clear presence of the element.

FIGURE 1

Example XPS spectrum of a CHCl₃ Treated Fibre.

From the atomic percentages, the surface concentration of species in terms of a unit segment of material (10 nm x 10 nm area) x 3.5 nm, the effective analysis depth can be calculated using a quantification approach that was developed previously [2]. Table 1 shows the results of the chloroform labelling in terms of the number of molecules adsorbed and the estimated volumes. Also presented are the segment concentrations of acid groups and "chemisorptive sites", the latter being equated with the uptake of H₂O molecules during aqueous labelling obtained in previous work [2].

At each DFT more than one specimen was analysed and the scatter in the results obtained is indicated in Figs. 2 and 3 which contain graphical presentations. The variability has contributions from both the reproducibility of the analytical technique and a statistical variation in composition of the different analysis areas along a given tow length.

The results of the labelling experiments, together with the observed uptake of water molecules by active sites possibly associated with microporous structure, led us to the conclusion that the treated fibre surface was saturated with oxygen containing groups, and had a high microporosity. It should be borne in mind that a perfect graphitic plane on the segment surface would contain 4000 carbon atoms.

The chloroform labelling experiments were designed to identify the rôle of micropores, and we consider that the molecules are retained within

FIGURE 2

Acid Group and Chemisorptive Site Concentrations, as a Function of the Degree of Fibre Surface Treatment (DFT).

the latter; there being no evidence of a chemical reaction between the reagent and surface functional groups since there are opposing trends in the respective concentrations. Despite the scatter there is a well defined

TABLE 1

Concentrations of Species on a $(10 \text{ nm})^2$ Unit Area of Fibre Surface as a Function of Treatment Level.

Treatment Level (DFT) %	O Atoms	COOH ¹ Groups	"Chemisorptive" ² Sites"	CHCl ₃ Molecules	$\frac{3V_{O1} \text{CHCl}_3}{10^{-5} \text{cm}^3 \text{g}^{-1}}$
0	2000	310	900	140	11
23	3400	340	1300	160	13
43	3500	470	1300	93	7.2
49	4400	570	1500	100	8.2
73	5600	540	1700	36	2.9
100	3900	540	2000	38	3.0

1 From barium labelling [2]; 2 H₂O uptake [2]; 3 CHCl₃ labelling (this work)

decrease in the detectable volume of CHCl₃ as DFT is raised from 0 to 100%. It is relatively simple to scale these results up to give molecule volumes in terms of cm³ per gram. As presented in Table 1, our values are in the range $(11 \text{ to } 3) \times 10^{-5} \text{cm}^3 \text{g}^{-1}$, which compare with $2 \times 10^{-5} \text{cm}^3 \text{g}^{-1}$ obtained by Rand and Robinson [3] on commercially treated Type I fibres, after degassing at 110°C using nitrogen adsorption-desorption tests.

An important factor in XPS analysis is that the CHCl₃ molecules must be retained on the fibres under the UHV conditions $\sim 10^{-9}$ torr, in the spectrometer chamber. A molecular binding energy of at least 1 eV is required, and it is proposed that this is achieved as a result of an enhanced binding effect, due to the well-known overlap of adsorption fields from opposite sides of a micropore which is just wider than the molecule, in addition to a "hydrogen bond" being formed between the polar CHCl₃ (1.01 Debye dipole moment, from standard texts), and functional groups which are associated with the micropores.

In the oxidative treatment process in which active oxygen is evolved at the fibre surface, oxygen containing functional groups, e.g. COOH, C=O and C-OH form on the surface carbon atoms. However, evolution of CO₂ is known to occur [5] leading to a general erosion of the carbon substrate, and we propose that this results in a widening of the upper regions of micropores, with a consequent negation of the enhanced binding effect, and reduced retention of chloroform molecules.

Synonymous with this is an increase in surface area, and available

FIGURE 3

Concentration of Chloroform Detected after Labelling, versus DFT.

FIGURE 4

Surface Structure Model.

sites for binding the functional groups. It is asserted that this CO₂ evolution becomes relatively more dominant at higher DFT values, resulting in a slight decrease in the oxygen concentration, remaining on the fibre at 100% DFT. Note that DFT is related to the amount of active oxygen evolved per unit tow length, during treatment.

In view of the x-ray diffraction work of Johnson and co-workers eg.[6] we have adopted a structure model in which graphitic sheets run essentially parallel to the "surface plane". A hypothetically perfect plane on the surface of our model (10 nm)² area segment would contain 4000 carbon atoms as mentioned previously and as there are 2000 oxygen atoms present in all forms on the segment even on an untreated fibre, it is suggested that the "surface plane" actually undulates and contains imperfections to which functional groups attach. The proposition of Johnson and Tyson [6] in which there are crystallites of average width 6.5 nm, stacked end to end, with intercrystallite voids ≤ 1 nm wide, enables the model to be developed further since this type of micro-structure could extend to the surface region. Hence the micropores detected using molecular probes are in fact these voids. A surface segment model is shown in Fig.4 which can also explain the rôle of surface oxidation.

An improved degree of adhesion between the fibres and an epoxy resin matrix following oxidation can be understood in the context of this overall model, as there is then a considerably higher concentration of reactive groups and active carbon atoms/chemisorptive sites, which can form chemical bonds with the resin molecules. Additionally the partial removal of a weak graphite skin could play a rôle in the enhancement of the interfacial bond strength.

Interfacial Bond Strengths from Scanning SIMS of Fracture Surfaces

In a preliminary experiment a sample of fibre tow only was analysed by static SIMS to identify which secondary ions are emitted and their relative intensities. The negative ion spectrum obtained is shown in Fig.5.

It is apparent that the mass peak at 26 amu, attributed to CN⁻ is the most intense in this case, which indicated that in a study of fracture surfaces, by mapping the emission of this species, the location of fibres could be identified. Other ions such as C₂H⁻ could also be considered as candidate ions for imaging fibres. Additionally, a secondary anion is required which is characteristic of the matrix but not of the fibre, or at least, one which is emitted with a relatively low intensity by the latter. This epoxy resin matrix is made by cross-linking a prepolymer which has been

FIGURE 5
Static SIMS Spectrum of a Carbon Fibre Tow.

formed by condensing epichlorohydrin with Bisphenol A, and thus it can be appreciated that the fragmentation pattern of this in SIMS analysis would probably contain some of the anions which also arise from the fibres, such as C_2H^- , for example.

In the first scanning characterisation of composite fractures, the suitability of various secondary ions for identifying the two components in the specimens was investigated and it emerged that Cl^- and CN^- were the most appropriate as the former is an impurity characteristic of the resin. A relatively small Cl^- peak, at mass number 35, was also present in the fibre spectrum, but this was considered to be insignificant for the proposed study. Images were therefore obtained of Cl^- and CN^- anions over selected analysis areas ($\approx(100 \mu m \times 100 \mu m)$) in size from the three composite fracture surfaces available, containing untreated, intermediate and lightly treated fibres. Converting the two images into green and red colour scales respectively in a computer overlay routine produces corresponding images which show the spatial relationship between the contrasting surface elements of fibre and matrix. Areas where the two signals coincide are therefore indicated by yellow. (For the purposes of reproduction here, the original green and red colour scales are presented as two grey scales).

From an untreated, UT fibre sample, the micrograph in Fig.6 shows clear alternating bands of dark (CN^-) and light grey (Cl^-) corresponding to the location of fibres and resin within the analysis area. The width of the dark bands is indicative of the $\approx 7 \mu m$ fibre diameter. It is therefore clearly demonstrated that there are no resin overlayers, even as thin as a few nm, which is the analysis depth in SIMS, present on the fibres - something which would be impossible to prove with conventional electron microscopy. The interlaminar shear strength of the original specimen was relatively low at 77 MPa [4] and the SIMS fractograph is consistent with failure being initiated at the relatively weak interface and propagating along the surface of the fibres, which confirms an initial interpretation of the ILSS data. The Cl^-/CN^- map of an intermediately treated fibre specimen was essentially similar to that in Fig. 6 with clear alternating bands, showing again the absence of resin overlayers. Hence, although the interface is stronger here, reflected in a corresponding ILSS of 82 MPa [4] failure initiation probably occurs at the interface which is still weaker than the strength of the matrix.

Moving onto the highly oxidised fibres, the overlay image, Fig.7, is quite different from those obtained in the two previous cases. Whilst the

overall signal strength was not as high as that attained for Fig.6, it is quite apparent that there is now a considerable degree of coincidence between the two ion signals where there are white areas. This corresponds to a thin or partial resin overlayer, of thickness of the order of molecule dimension. There are still some portions of fibre which are "clean" (dark grey) and others which have a substantial amount of matrix adhered (light grey) but the resin overlayers of \sim nm thickness could only be reliably detected by the SIMS technique. In this case the ILSS of the original specimen had reached a limiting value of $>93\text{MPa}$ [4] where the composite strength is probably determined by the essentially constant fracture toughness of the resin, since the interfacial bond strength is larger at this level of fibre treatment and a cohesive fracture is initiated, leaving overlayers on the fibres. The "clean" fibre areas could imply either a localised initiation of failure at surface defects, or that the shear strength of the matrix is only just greater than that of the adhesive interface.

It has therefore been directly demonstrated that the interfacial bond strength increases by oxidising the reinforcing fibres, ultimately becoming greater than that of the other components in the system. Examination of the transverse failure process in situ in an SEM is being carried out in parallel studies to quantify the interfacial bond strength. Preliminary results confirm that the highly treated fibres form a relatively strong bond.

CONCLUSIONS

The XPS based study has revealed a structure model for fibre surface chemistry and an associated micropore structure which can be reconciled with models presented in the literature, from XRD investigations. Changes brought about by oxidative treatment, which lead to an increased surface functionality, especially with regard to COOH groups and concentration of active or chemisorptive sites, can be related to an "opening up" of the micropores, together with a partial removal of a weak graphitic skin. The microstructural study of the interface, covering scanning SIMS of fracture surfaces, has conclusively shown that the composite interfacial bond strength is raised as a result of fibre oxidation, which indicates that the two species referred to above probably play the major rôle in the bond formation, since it is their combined concentrations which reaches a maximum at the higher treatment levels, from Fig. 2. It should be noted that

acid group concentration alone is at a plateau, for DFT \geq 49%.

In particular, the excellent applicability of the SIMS approach has been demonstrated in the context of fractography and the relative interface: matrix strength can be inferred from the chemical maps obtained, and related to the ultimate composite shear strength, and degree of fibre treatment.

Overall, we have made a significant advance in understanding the true and probably complex nature of the interface and have shown the importance of microstructural studies.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was conducted with the financial support of the Procurement Executive, Ministry of Defence. We are also grateful to Drs. G. Dorey and J. Harvey of the Royal Aircraft Establishment, Farnborough for the provision of materials and test specimens.